

Contents lists available at ScienceDirect

Spectrochimica Acta Part A: Molecular and Biomolecular Spectroscopy

journal homepage: www.journals.elsevier.com/spectrochimica-acta-part-a-molecular-and-biomolecular-spectroscopy

Signature of electronically excited states in Raman spectra of azobenzene derivatives. Computational and experimental approaches

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GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Azobenzene derivatives
Raman spectra
Excited states
Vibrational fingerprints
Coupling effect

ABSTRACT

Raman spectroscopy can provide highly sensitive and detailed information about the structural fingerprint of molecules, enabling their identification. In this study, our aim is to understand the enhanced intensity observed in experimental Raman measurements. Five azobenzene derivatives were selected, each substituted with different functional groups, for both experimental and theoretical investigations. To reproduce the experimental trend, we employed various levels of theory using the QM-DFT approach. Theoretical results were compared to experimental data through both qualitative and quantitative analyses. A good correlation between theoretical and experimental results was achieved when considering electronic transitions to predict the theoretical Raman spectra and interpret the experimental data. Our theoretical results indicate that even dark ($n\pi^*$) transitions, which are forbidden and have an oscillator strength close to zero, can have a signature in the Raman spectra due to the resonance effect with incident energy. Additionally, the vibrational modes stimulated by the presence of

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.saa.2025.125828>

Received 26 July 2024; Accepted 30 January 2025

Available online 31 January 2025

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$\pi\pi^*$ bright states, being at the pre-resonance with the incident energy, was clearly separated from the vibrational frequencies of the dark states, which was evinced in the Raman fingerprint. Theoretical Raman spectra of azobenzene derivatives, substituted with push–pull moieties, revealed contributions from the charge transfer transitions ($n\pi^*$ CT, $\pi\pi^*$ CT) as well as back-donation of electron density, observed for the first time in an azobenzene derivative. Our protocol, proposing a quantitative and qualitative overlap between theoretical and experimental data, confirms the presence of combination modes between vibrational levels and electronically excited states.

1. Introduction

Scientific community focuses increasingly to harness solar energy. This scope to convert the light from the Sun into energy is free and sustainable. Hence, we need to try to learn how to efficiently transfer the nature machinery into technologies to gain electricity from light. Switchable compounds, designed into adequate materials, could harness the power of the sun and transform it into artificial energy and electricity.

Azobenzene archetypes function as molecular switchable materials and can be used to create new systems, capable to harvest solar light to generate electricity [1–6]. The azobenzene molecular system is recognized for its typically *trans* and *cis* conformations, which can be converted from one to the other by applying an external source.

Concerning the electronic properties described by UV–Vis absorption spectra, the azobenzene molecule exhibits two well-separated absorption bands that permit selective irradiations. An intense band appearing in the UV range (~300–400 nm) corresponds to a $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ symmetry-allowed transition ($S_0 \rightarrow S_2$), while another band, lower in intensity, localizes in the visible region (400–500 nm), which is convenient for the $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition ($S_0 \rightarrow S_1$). [7–17]. Therefore, the azobenzene photochromic molecular system can be switchable during irradiation, simultaneously changing the electronic configuration after visiting excited state energy levels. Moreover, the presence of substituents in different positions on the azobenzene skeleton complicates the understanding of the photochemical properties and the isomerization mechanism. This situation appears as an effect of intramolecular modification of electronic configurations inside the molecule. However, besides using UV–Vis spectra, several studies on different types of azobenzene derivatives have been performed, aiming to include vibration modes (especially Raman) relating to the electronic excitation [18–23]. All the above studies indicate that azobenzene derivatives can provide a unique fingerprint of molecular vibrations and to enhance Raman signals when vibrational transitions couple with electronic excitations. Additionally, all these works provide information about the structural changes of the molecule, the relationship between structure and molecular species that could form during the isomerization reaction, as well as the types of electronic transitions and vibration modes that occur upon photoexcitation. To the best of our knowledge, details about the vibrational-electronic coupling effect have not been described in previous works of azobenzene compounds. Here, we can see how the excited states

energies of a molecule during electronic vibrational coupling are distributed among several vibrational modes. These details could provide valuable information about the intrinsic internal parameters that define molecular topology. Understanding the modification of internal parameters that occur before and after excitation could improve knowledge about the mechanisms involved in the *trans* \leftrightarrow *cis* conversion reactions.

Coupling electronic and vibrational transitions in a single measurement, such as Raman scattering, a good sensitivity for the spectroscopic interrogation of light-absorbing chromophores can be obtained [24]. This strategy can be realized when the laser light has a frequency close to the energy corresponding to the electronic transition, a phenomenon known from resonance Raman measurements [24–26]. Moreover, the resonant Raman effect can provide intuitive information about the properties of molecular systems in the interplay between the ground and excited electronic states [27,28]. The Raman fingerprint results can explain how a class of compounds (in the present study: the azobenzene derivatives) works as molecular motors stimulated by light and later can be used in different applications. Putting all data resulted from theoretical and experimental determinations into a representative library permits us to create and to provide such design rulebook in order to extract and to elucidate the fingerprints of vibration modes and to predict the modification of the internal parameters along the excitation process. To have a comprehensive library on a molecule, including more information about the intrinsic properties, this work aims to explore the interplay between the vibronic transition and the electronic excitations of the azobenzene derivatives during the on and pre-resonance Raman process. Our theoretical calculations reveal a good concordance with experimental data, and confirm the presence of combination modes derived from contributions of the ground and excited state interplay. Both main transitions, $n\pi^*$ and $\pi\pi^*$ specific for azobenzene derivatives as well as for $\pi\pi^*$ CT and $n\pi^*$ CT, contribute to the signal in the Raman spectra. Experimental and theoretical results showed an increase in intensity when the incident frequency was closer to the vertical electronic excitation, even if this transition had a symmetry-forbidden character. The theoretical results were corroborated with experimental data through a both qualitative and quantitative overlap. Moreover, it is important from a fundamental point of view to understand the intramolecular processes, including the energies of electronic and vibronic levels, employed in the irradiation process.

Fig. 1. Azobenzene derivatives selected for investigation.

Fig. 2. A schematic representation including the allowed vibrations coupled with electronic transitions ($S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ and $S_0 \rightarrow S_2$) as a function of excitation energy in the Raman spectra, in the case of azobenzene derivatives.

Table 1

Quantitative results of correlation between computational and experimental Raman spectra predicted at 442 nm (scaling factor in the range 0.8–1.2).

Basis set	Functional	Scale Factor	Average R
6-311G(dp)	APFD	0.9390	0.4526
	B3LYP	0.980	0.5318
	BMK	0.9370	0.2593
	CAM-B3LYP	0.9860	0.5316
	M062X	0.9820	0.5086
	MN12SX	0.9370	0.5518
	MN15L	0.9720	0.6376
	PBE0	0.9330	0.3935
	wB97XD	0.9880	0.5281
cc-pVTZ	APFD	0.9500	0.4187
	B3LYP	0.9820	0.5316
	BMK	0.9500	0.2806
	CAM-B3LYP	0.9870	0.509
	M062X	0.9850	0.5077
	MN12SX	0.9410	0.5812
	MN15L	0.9810	0.6450
	PBE0	0.9410	0.5692
	wB97XD	0.990	0.5214
Def2TZVP	APFD	0.9690	0.455
	B3LYP	0.9810	0.5361
	BMK	0.9460	0.4197
	CAM-B3LYP	0.9860	0.5183
	M062X	0.9840	0.5112
	MN12SX	0.9400	0.5042
	MN15L	0.99800	0.5932
	PBE0	0.9350	0.5156
	wB97XD	0.98900	0.5263

2. Computational protocol and experimental details

Five azobenzene derivatives have been included in this work: unsubstituted azobenzene (**Azo**); 4-phenylazomaleinanil (**Azo-4**) [azobenzene substituted with $-I$ inductive maleimide group]; Disperse Orange 3 (**Azo-3**) [azobenzene with push (NH_2)-pull (N_2O) substituents]; 4-(4-nitrophenylazo)-1-naphthol (**Azo-44**) [azobenzene derivative with

Fig. 3. a) Comparison between experimental and theoretical Raman excitation profiles obtained from MN15L/cc-pVTZ calculations for **Azo** compound; b) fundamental bands alongside the contributions from excited states and experimental measurements.

Fig. 4. Representation of the vibrational modes of Azo compound computed using the MN15L/cc-pVTZ method.

naphthalene unit and functional withdrawing electron ($-N_2O$) group and sensitive to pH ($-OH$); **Disperse Red 19** {**Azo-19**} [Azobenzene substituted with electron withdrawing ($-N_2O$) functional group and sensitive to pH ($-OH$)] (Fig. 1).

The theoretical calculations include the geometry optimization steps, frequency determination (in order to predict the validity of the optimized geometries), where no imaginary values were obtained in the Hessian matrix, Raman spectra for fingerprint vibrations, theoretical UV-Vis absorption spectra for electronic configuration of the excited states. All these computational approaches described above were performed using the Gaussian G16 simulation engine [29]. The azo derivative **Azo-19** having two $-CH_2-CH_2-$ sequences and OH group, more rotamers can be adopted. Therefore, a search for the lowest energy chemical structure was realized with the CREST program based on the semi-empirical GFN-xTB methods [30,31]. The lowest rotamers were afterwards optimized with density functional theory (DFT) methods and the equilibrium geometry with the lowest energy was selected. Multiple levels of DFT have been included in this work: namely APFD [32], B3LYP [33], CAM-B3LYP [34], PBE0 [35], BMK [36], M062X [37], MN12SX [38], MN15L [39], wb97XD [40]. Together with these functionals, the electronic wave functions were estimated according to Pople et al. (6-311G(d,p) [41], Ahlrichs et al. (Def2TZVP) [42], and Dunning et al. (cc-pVTZ) [43] basis sets. Vertical excitations were estimated in order to respect the experimental conditions and were performed with the polarizable continuum model (PCM) [44] using the integral equation formalism variant (IEFPCM) [45] based on the time-dependent density functional theory (TD-DFT), IEFPCM/TD-DFT.

Special attention was given to interrogate the Raman spectra and subsequently to extract the unique vibrational fingerprints of azobenzene moieties from these results. Both experimental and theoretical

Raman spectra were used to obtain the fingerprints of azobenzene moieties. The Raman vibrations obtained by theoretical calculations have been used to correlate with the experimental measurements. Therefore, a qualitative representation could be achieved by visually overlaying the theoretical and experimental Raman data. But this point can be subjective, and for greater accuracy, a quantitative comparison would be more appropriate. Regularly, a comparison between theoretical and experimental vibrational spectra is conducted by scaling with a correction factor to compensate for the harmonic approximation and to ensure that the both methods provide adequate overlapping. But in this case, the correction factor strongly depends on method (e.g., functional used in DFT level of theory) as well as the basis set. To overcome this situation, some studies have included the different statistical correlation coefficients: Pearson and Spearman, to match the experimental measurements [46–50], the Pearson correlation coefficient being the most suitable and commonly used. But, for qualitative representations between experimental and theoretical vibrations as well as to obtain adequate quantitative results a task book must be respected. Beatriz von der Esch et al designed such as guideline set in order to obtain a quantitative comparison, especially for IR spectra [51]. Therefore, to quantitatively compare the experimental Raman spectra with the theoretical spectra, we utilized a script developed by our group named SpectraCorrM, written in the Python programming language (details provided in Supporting Information, Fig. SI 1). For a thorough qualitative and quantitative comparison between theoretical and experimental Raman spectra, a protocol was followed (further details described in the Supporting Information). The experimental details are also outlined in the Supporting Information document.

Theoretical vertical excitations employed in UV-Vis absorption spectra were calculated using TD-DFT. Frontier molecular orbitals

Fig. 5. a) Comparison between experimental and theoretical Raman excitation profiles obtained from MN15L/cc-pVTZ calculations for **Azo-4**; b) fundamental bands alongside the contributions from excited states and experimental measurements.

suitable for electronic transitions were assessed using the Natural Transition Orbitals (NTOs) approach, which provides a more intuitive representation of excited states of molecules [52]. NTOs were appraised using the Multiwfn code [53] and depicted with Avogadro software [54].

Raman spectra were obtained on and pre-resonance using the harmonic approximation with the FC class 3 program [55]. The theoretical vibrational resonance Raman spectra have been computed considering both specific transitions: $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ ($S_0 \rightarrow S_2$) and $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ ($S_0 \rightarrow S_1$) of the azobenzene derivatives. DFT and TD-DFT levels were employed to compute vibronic modes and generate theoretical Raman spectra. In order to respect the experimental conditions of excitation at resonance, the theoretical Raman spectrum was obtained mimicking the incident value of frequency at 442 nm. The resonance Raman spectrum along the $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition was computed by including the incident energy at 442 nm to observe if this type of excitation could induce a signature (pre-resonance effects could appear) in the experimental excitation-vibration mode measurements. Time independent (TI) approach including Franck-Condon (FC) and Herzberg-Teller (HT) effect [28,56] together with Vertical Gradient (VG) model [57,58] have been used to predict the computed vibrational resonance Raman spectrum on and pre-resonance. Huang Rhys factor has been included in the Raman calculations to determine and characterize the strength of the electron-vibronic coupling. Unless specified otherwise, DFT and TD-DFT calculations were performed in dichloromethane (DCM) using an implicit solvent model to align with experimental measurements.

3. Results and discussion

The Raman spectra were extracted from the theoretical calculations based on multi-level theories for all the five azobenzene derivatives. The comparison of theoretical and experimental results was realized using

the polarization of molecules coming from the incident laser frequency. The reason for this selection will be described later in the text.

3.1. Raman and resonant scattering vibrational spectra

Theoretical Raman calculations in the first stage of this work were based on quantum mechanics (QM) calculations, including multiple levels of theory (functionals and basis sets). Two approaches were considered to compute the intensities and vibration modes of the Raman spectra: (i) some calculations for molecules which were not polarized by the incident frequency, and (ii) the molecules were polarized by incident frequencies of 442, 633, and 785 nm. The last three types of incident lasers were added to mimic the experimental conditions and to determine which method can offer reliable results (both frequency wavenumbers and Raman mode intensities) in comparison with reference (experimental) data. However, the predictions of the Raman intensities at specific wavelengths of incident light can be achieved through dynamic frequency calculations (known as pre-resonance Raman calculations) and can provide an initial overview how the theoretical level can well reproduce the experimental measurements, but details about the contributions of electronic transitions are not surprised.

The experimental Raman spectra showed comparable intensities when incident frequencies of 442 nm, 633 nm, and 785 nm were used. However, in different wave number regions (1400–1600 cm^{-1}), the intensity of the Raman spectra at 442 nm was slightly higher, especially in the case of azobenzene derivatives **Azo-4**, **Azo-3**, **Azo-19**, and **Azo-44** (Figs. SI 2–6). Because azobenzene derivatives show an electronic transition that occurs at a wavelength close to the frequency of the incident laser at 442 nm, an increase in the intensity of Raman signals was observed due to the resonance effect (electronic excitations couple with vibrational transitions). The experimental UV-Vis spectra in DCM for all five azobenzene derivatives were represented in Figs. SI 7–11 to validate the presence of the first low-lying transitions into the visible range. This transition can be matched by the frequency of the incident laser at 442 nm in the case of the molecular systems **Azo**, **Azo-4**, **Azo-3**, **Azo-19**, and compound **Azo-44**. A diagram depicting the allowed vibrations coupled with the electronic transitions as a function of excitation energy in the Raman spectra was illustrated for azobenzene derivatives in Fig. 2.

This diagram illustrates: (i) conventional Raman scattering occurring when there are transitions from a vibronic ground state to virtual states; (ii) pre-resonance effect, where the energy of the incident light used for measurement was close to the electronic transition, enhancing Raman signals; (iii) resonance Raman interplay, the incident frequency of the external source used for measurement aligns with an electronic transition energy, leading to enhanced Raman scattering; (iv) Raman fluorescence phenomena which involve interactions in the molecular system which absorbs incident photons, promoting them to electronically excited states.

In order to mimic the experimental conditions and evaluate the performance of theoretical models based on QM calculations, a representation of Raman intensities and wavenumbers was realized. Taking this aspect into account, a quantitative comparison was accomplished using Pearson-type statistics between the experimental measurements and the theoretical results. This comparison was realized without polarization effect included into calculation conditions and under resonance at 442 nm, where an increase in intensity occurred because this incident frequency coincided with $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ electronic transition appearing in the visible region for azobenzene derivatives. Another reason why the results obtained at 442 nm have been used for theoretical/experimental comparison was that unwanted signals such as induced fluorescence (due to the presence of $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ character, which leads to the opening of ultra-fast channels of non-radiative deexcitation after the energy absorption process) or background noise were somehow reduced. Even though, it is well known that the $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition has a small value of the oscillator strength (f) and it is recognized as a

Fig. 6. Representation of the vibrational modes of Azo-4 compound computed with the MN15L/cc-pVTZ method.

forbidden transition with a minimal contribution to electronic absorption. However, an enhancement of Raman intensity could occur when the Raman resonance effect was present. The comparison between experimental and theoretical determinations centered on the Raman vibrational fingerprint region ranging from 800 to 1800 cm^{-1} . The method that provided the closest results to the experimental data was assessed using Pearson-type statistical analysis after analysis of the calculated spectra and the experimental spectra within the 0.8–1.2 range. The quantitative results based on Pearson correlation after theoretical/experimental overlapping reveal that the MN15L/cc-pVTZ method was closer to experimental measurements (Table 1). The Pearson correlation coefficient using the MN15L/cc-pVTZ level was around $R = 0.6450$, with a scaling factor of 0.9810. The graphical representations of theoretical and experimental overlap from Figs. SI 12–16 exhibit a correlated arrangement. However, the comparison shown in Figs. SI 12–16 represents an overlap between theoretical pre-resonance Raman effects and experimental resonance scattering measurements.

To clarify the role of incident frequency in predicting theoretical Raman spectra, a comparison of the no polarization of Raman calculations with the experimental was carried out, data using the Pearson statistical approach, similar to the method employed for the 442 nm Raman spectra case. The values of the Pearson correlation coefficient from Table SI 1 indicate that a minor improvement can be achieved if the incident photon energy was not included in theoretical calculations for predicting Raman scattering spectra. The statistical values from Table SI 1 showed that the MN15L/cc-pVTZ level yielded the good

results. The average R obtained with the Pearson method was approximately 0.5761, being lower as compared to the computational result at 442 nm. This discrepancy was observed at the 1.7100 scaling factor. If we consider the same scaling factor, 0.9810, when the Pearson coefficient R was approximately 0.6450 as predicted by computational results using the incident frequency at 442 nm with the MN15L/cc-pVTZ level of theory, in the current case (comparing no polarization Raman spectra with experimental measurements at 442 nm), the average R value was 0.3674. This indicates that a good correlation can be achieved by introduce the incident photon energy in theoretical calculations. Therefore, it can be concluded that the polarization effect induced by the incident frequency plays an important role in predicting Raman spectra.

To gain a direct comparison (theory vs. experiment) in the Raman intensity profile, a representation of scattering spectra performed with the MN15L/cc-pVTZ method has been shown in Figs. SI 17–21. These graphical representations of the theoretical Raman spectra showed a similar intensity trend for compounds Azo, Azo-4, and Azo-3 as compared to experimental measurements. Specifically, the intensity of the scattering signal computed at the incident frequency of 442 nm was higher compared to 633 nm and 785 nm frequencies. Some differences appeared in the case of compounds Azo-19 and Azo-44, where the intensity of Raman signals predicted by MN15L/cc-pVTZ level calculated at 633 nm was higher relating to 442 nm. To understand this difference, other computational results obtained with the CAM-B3LYP/cc-pVTZ method have been analyzed in Figs. SI 22 and 23, the theoretical trends being now in line with the experimental data. The reason to select

Fig. 7. a) Comparison between experimental and theoretical Raman excitation profiles obtained from CAM-B3LYP/cc-pVTZ calculations for **Azo-3** compound; b) fundamental bands alongside the contributions from excited states and experimental measurements.

the CAM-B3LYP functional in the new Raman calculations was due to the presence of CT transitions (induced by the presence of push-pull functional groups, attached by azobenzene core especially in case of the derivatives **Azo-3**, **Azo-19** and **Azo-44**, respectively), which could influence the intensity order. It was previously shown by us [8] that the CAM-B3LYP functional can explain the presence of CT states in azobenzene derivatives. Recent works, for the TD-DFT-CAM-B3LYP level, gives reasonable results for predictions of CT states [59,60]. Analyzing the results of theoretical resonance Raman spectra from Figs. SI 17–22, no frequency shift was observed upon changing the incident frequency.

Before predicting the Raman resonance spectra, the electronic transitions at the MN15L/cc-pVTZ level of theory were inspected in details. The theoretical results included NTOs representations of the electronic transitions and the corresponding values of excitation energies, Figs. SI 24–28. The NTO results suggested the presence of an $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition corresponding to the $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ excitation in compound **Azo** around 428 nm with an oscillator strength (f) of 0 (Fig. SI24). In compounds **Azo-3**, **Azo-4**, **Azo-19**, and **Azo-44**, the $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ excitation exhibits $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ (charge transfer, CT) character (Figs. SI 25–28). The wavelength value corresponding to this type $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition appeared at 493 nm ($f = 0.9300$) in the case of compound **Azo-3**, 485 nm ($f = 0.0011$) for azobenzene derivative **Azo-4**, 540 nm ($f = 0.9923$), and 531 nm ($f = 0.7123$) for the molecular system **Azo-44**. The vertical $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ electronic transitions following the $S_0 \rightarrow S_2$ electronic excitation were observed specifically for compound **Azo** at $\lambda = 349$ nm, which is a characteristic strong absorption band with an $f = 0.9602$ (Fig. SI 24). On the other hand, in the case of $S_0 \rightarrow S_2$ photoexcitation, the character of this vertical transition was $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ CT in the next situations: with $f = 0.0001$ and $\lambda =$

483 nm for compound **Azo-4**, while in the case of compound **Azo-3** the value of f was around 0.0024 and happens at $\lambda = 489$ nm, for compound **Azo-19** $f = 0.0030$ ($\lambda = 491$ nm), and for compound **Azo-44** appears at $\lambda = 531$ nm having the $f = 0$ (Figs. SI 25–28). Hence, it can be observed that in the excitations $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ and $S_0 \rightarrow S_2$, which are typical for the photo excited states of azobenzene, transitions such as $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ CT and $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ CT can occur, often with oscillator strength values close to 0. Because these transitions are forbidden, they are expected to bring only a minor contribution to the resonance Raman spectra.[26] However, we did not exclude these transitions from our resonance Raman calculations, as they play a role in the electronic configuration of azobenzene derivatives and could align with the incident excitation energy of interest, such as 442 nm. Therefore, additional excited states were explored in the theoretical UV-Vis spectra, including $S_0 \rightarrow S_3$ and $S_0 \rightarrow S_4$ transitions, in order to identify transitions with oscillator strength values significantly above 0. Theoretical calculation results showed in the Figs. SI 26–28 indicated that the $S_0 \rightarrow S_3$ transitions were $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ nature in compounds **Azo-3** (with intrinsic parameter $f = 0.4183$, $\lambda = 361$ nm), **Azo-19** ($f = 0.4192$, $\lambda = 385$ nm), and respectively for **Azo-44** derivative ($f = 0.1336$, $\lambda = 386$ nm). For the compound **Azo-4**, the $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ type transitions occur through $S_0 \rightarrow S_3$ vertical electronic hopping with $f = 0$ and $\lambda = 430$ nm, whilst the $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ appear in the $S_0 \rightarrow S_4$ transition at $\lambda = 370$ nm with $f = 1.1772$ (Fig. SI 25). These additionally selected transitions have $f \gg 0$ (with exception of the $S_0 \rightarrow S_3$ interplay from compound **Azo-4**), and they can put the signature into Raman spectrum through the pre-resonance effect. As a short overview, the theoretical results obtained with MN15L/cc-pVTZ method reveal that the all $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ excitations energies were close to the incident frequency used in the experimental Raman spectra.

3.2. Vibrational fingerprint and coupling effect along the electronic excitations in the on and pre-resonance Raman spectra

In the next stage, we included the signatures of electronically excited states, observed in the azobenzene derivatives in the theoretical Raman spectra, to determine their contributions to the final vibrational profile. The transition moments in the vibrational resonance Raman spectra were modeled using the HTi (Franck-Condon + Herzberg-Teller) approach around the initial state geometry, as well as the HTf (Franck-Condon + Herzberg-Teller) model around the final state geometry in the case of forbidden transitions. The FC level was included for an intense transition. The spectra were predicted taking into consideration the vibrational coupling effect along with the electronic excitations. Theoretical frequencies were scaled by a factor of 0.9810 relative to the experimental values. Next, we introduced the label ν for different frequencies to provide a clear description. Moreover, the Huang-Rhys factor (S) was also predicted from computational results to characterize the electron-phonon (vibronic) coupling effect [61–64].

Compound Azo. For the unsubstituted azobenzene compound **Azo**, the theoretical results agree with the experimental measurements under certain conditions (Fig. 3). In defining the final band shape, both the $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ excitation in resonance with the incident frequency and the $S_0 \rightarrow S_2$ transition at pre-resonance participate. In a specific situation, the vibrational modes that appeared after the vibrational-electronic coupling effect following the $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ and $S_0 \rightarrow S_2$ excitations aligned with experimental results in the 800–1800 cm^{-1} domain, characteristic of fingerprints. However, the intensity of some bands in 800–1000 cm^{-1} range was higher when $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition state was included in the theoretical calculations. A good correlation was achieved by comparing the theoretical band shapes and positions of frequencies resulting from the $S_0 \rightarrow S_2$ process in the wavenumber domains between 800–1500 cm^{-1} (frequencies like ν_2 - ν_6 showed comparable intensities to the experiment). In the region of 1400–1500 cm^{-1} , the contribution of the first low-lying excitation in prediction of intensity was small (Fig. 3a). The data relating to the S factors after the Raman prediction were plotted in Fig. SI 29, and the vibrational modes are shown in Fig. 4. The

Fig. 8. Representation of the vibrational modes of Azo-3 compound computed with the CAM-B3LYP/cc-PVTZ method.

vibrational ν_1 mode has been observed experimentally at 1590 cm^{-1} resulting from the contribution of $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition, theoretically estimated at 1600 cm^{-1} with an S factor around 0.15 (slightly higher like in the $\pi\pi^*$ character). The electronic excitation $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ contributes to the ν_2 - ν_4 vibrational fingerprint region associated with symmetrical stretching vibration of $-N=N-$ in the case of ν_2 and ν_4 , while for ν_3 , asymmetrical stretching vibrations of $-N=N-$ occurs (Fig. 4). The ν_2 vibrational mode was theoretically estimated at around 1506 cm^{-1} , while experimentally it was observed at 1489 cm^{-1} . In Fig. 3a, the ν_4 vibration appeared experimentally at 1438 and computationally at 1444 cm^{-1} . The S factor was 0.36 for ν_2 , 0.69, 0.20 for ν_3 , and 0.69 for ν_4 , indicates a strong electronic-vibrational coupling following the $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ interaction. The S factor for $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ type was higher as compared to the contribution of $n \rightarrow$

π^* transition, despite the excitation occurring at the pre-resonance incident frequency, due to the symmetry allowed transition and dipole effect. Another set of vibration modes observed in the Azo structure were located experimentally at 1181 cm^{-1} and theoretically around 1190 cm^{-1} , labeled as ν_5 , as well as at 1141 cm^{-1} (experimentally) and 1138 cm^{-1} (theoretically), labeled as ν_6 . These vibrations correspond to C-N and N-C asymmetrical stretching vibrations (Fig. 4). The S factor for ν_5 indicated a value around 0.17, while for the ν_4 mode it was 0.59, the $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ excitation contributing most significantly to the Raman spectra, Fig. SI 29. Details from Fig. 3b exhibit that the presence of fundamental and combination modes predominated in the final Raman spectra. Moreover, the theoretical results obtained with MN15L density functional method in the case of fundamental vibrational transitions were in

Fig. 9. a) Comparison between experimental and theoretical Raman excitation profiles obtained from CAM-B3LYP/cc-pVTZ calculations for **Azo-19** compound; b) fundamental bands alongside the contributions from excited states and experimental measurements.

line with experimental data representation (Fig. 3a and b). The FCHT transition moment model was utilized for the $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ transition on resonance conditions and FC level in the case of $S_0 \rightarrow S_2$ excitation under pre-resonance, with an incident frequency of 442 nm for the **Azo** compound.

Compound Azo-4. This derivative belongs to the family of azobenzene compounds according to the classification by Rau, Bandara, and Burdette [10], because its absorption spectra are similar to those of the unsubstituted form (Figs. SI 7 and 8). Even though maleimide has been a small but significant inductive effect and did not bring substantial changes to the UV-Vis spectrum, it still seems that the Raman spectrum was more complex.

In Fig. 5, the comparison of theoretical results with experimental data was showed. In the calculations of the theoretical Raman spectra, all vertical electronic excitations depicted in Fig. SI 25 were included. Some of the computational results were overestimated in comparison with the experimental vibrations, especially for the S_1 state ($\pi\pi^*$ CT). However, a closer agreement with the experimental data was obtained by including the S_2 ($n\pi^*$ CT), S_3 ($n\pi^*$), and S_4 ($\pi\pi^*$) in the Raman calculations. The vibrational mode ν_4 was precisely reproduced by the resonance effect with the incident frequency of the electronic $S_0 \rightarrow S_3$ excitation, as well as reasonably by the S_1 ($\pi\pi^*$) and S_2 ($n\pi^*$) states. This vibration appeared in the experimental spectra at 1600 cm^{-1} and was computationally predicted at 1598 cm^{-1} . The vibration mode ν_4 represented the most important vibration of the azo bond, namely a $-N=N-$ asymmetrical stretching. The ν_2 and ν_3 vibration modes were predicted solely at the theoretical level and can be found by small shoulders observed in the experimental spectra. Additionally, these mode ν_2 and ν_3 could

arise from combination frequencies stimulated by the S_1 – S_3 states with fundamental vibrations states (Fig. 5). The graphical representation of the vibrational modes in Fig. 6 shows that both ν_2 (1512 cm^{-1}) and ν_3 (1499 cm^{-1}) correspond to the symmetrical stretching mode of the $-N=N-$ bond. On the other hand, the vibration bands labeled ν_4 to ν_6 represent the $-N=N-$ asymmetrical stretching bond, all aligning with the experimental measurements. Significant contribution for these vibration modes was coming from the pre-resonance of S_4 ($\pi\pi^*$) transition. In the ν_7 frequency, the dominant vibration corresponds to the symmetrical stretching vibration of the C (azobenzene core)–N (maleimide unit) bond, which it was not depicted here. The vibrational modes involving the C–N and N–C vibrations from the central C–N=N–C dihedral angle experimentally appear at 1189 cm^{-1} (for ν_8) and 1147 cm^{-1} (for ν_9). These were well reproduced computationally, especially in terms of contributions from the S_3 ($n\pi^*$) and S_4 ($\pi\pi^*$) states, which predicted frequencies of 1193 cm^{-1} for ν_8 and 1139 cm^{-1} for ν_9 respectively. In ν_8 , the mode corresponds to C–N and N–C asymmetrical stretching, while in ν_9 , it corresponds to C–N and N–C symmetrical stretching vibrations (Fig. 6). The S factor values around 1600 cm^{-1} showed a slight increase as compared to the unsubstituted **Azo** compound. Conversely, in the wavenumber range of 1300 – 1500 cm^{-1} , the S factors were either smaller or comparable to those observed for the azo derivative (Figs. SI 29 and 30). According to Fig. 5b, the presence of fundamental vibrational bands correlates well with the experimental data. The FC transition moment model was utilized for the $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ transition on resonance conditions, and for $S_0 \rightarrow S_4$ excitation under pre-resonance. The FCHT level was applied in case of $S_0 \rightarrow S_2$, $S_0 \rightarrow S_3$ both vertical transition in resonance with the incident frequency of 442 nm for the **Azo-4** compound. Based on the discussion above in the Raman spectra of the azoderivative **Azo-4**, combination modes of fundamental and excited transitions following the $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$, $S_0 \rightarrow S_2$, $S_0 \rightarrow S_3$, and $S_0 \rightarrow S_4$ excitations appeared in the spectrum.

Compounds Azo-3, 19, and 44. Due to the presence of push–pull functional groups on the azobenzene core, these molecular systems belong to the pseudo-stilbene class [10]. The Raman spectra are represented in Figs. SI 31–33, and they are quite different in comparison with the unsubstituted form (Fig. 3). Graphical representations from Figs. 31–33 of Raman spectra, including the resonance and pre-resonance effect, show an underestimated behavior between theoretical results and experimental measurements. Due to the fact that the intensity of Raman scattering spectra was not well predicted by the MN15L/cc-pVTZ method, and because the CT states appear during the excitation process in all three compounds (**Azo-3**, **Azo-19**, and **Azo-44**), we have performed calculations using the CAM-B3LYP/cc-pVTZ level of theory. In this case, the electronic configurations in the ground and excited states were again analyzed using the CAM-B3LYP/cc-pVTZ methodology (Table SI 2). NTO values shown in Table SI 2, confirm the presence of the $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ and $S_0 \rightarrow S_2$ excitations as the majority during the excitation process. However, the graphical representations of Raman spectra in Figs. SI 34–36 again show a moderate agreement between theoretical results and experimental measurements. Hence, we have included other electronic transition types in the vibrational spectra, where new excitation processes were added (Fig. SI 37). Fig. SI 37 shows a CT character for these new states, with the charge transfer occurring from the nitro group to the azobenzene core ($nNO_2\pi^*$ CT). Apparently, these transitions involve an opposite direction of charge flow induced by vibrational motion (quenching the azobenzene \rightarrow nitro CT transfer [$\pi\pi^*$ CT]) and have been observed in organic compounds substituted with a nitro moiety [65]. Taking into consideration this new transition, which has oscillator strength closer to 0, presented in compounds **Azo-3**, **Azo-19**, and **Azo-44** in the vibrational resonance Raman spectra, the agreement between theoretical results and experimental data was improved.

In the Raman spectra, resonance and pre-resonance effects occur in the case of compound **Azo-3** (Fig. 7a). The vibrational mode ν_1 appears experimentally at 1590 cm^{-1} and is predicted with the CAM-B3LYP/cc-

Fig. 10. Representation of the vibrational modes of **Azo-19** compound computed with the CAM-B3LYP/cc-pVTZ method.

pVTZ method at 1551 cm^{-1} , including the $S_0 \rightarrow S_2$ transition. The ν_1 vibrational mode stimulated by the electronic $S_0 \rightarrow S_2$ transition favors a $-\text{N}=\text{N}-$ symmetrical stretching frequency. In the case of the ν_2 mode, it appears in the experimental Raman spectrum at 1515 cm^{-1} , while the theoretically at 1538 cm^{-1} , which includes the $-\text{N}=\text{N}-$ asymmetrical stretching vibration. The S_2 and S_3 states contribute to all the aforementioned vibration modes. The ν_3 vibration mode, observed experimentally at 1448 cm^{-1} , shows a predominant contribution from the S_1 ($n\pi^*$) state, favoring the appearance of asymmetrical stretching of the $-\text{N}=\text{N}-$ bond at 1446 cm^{-1} as predicted by the CAM-B3LYP/cc-pVTZ method. Another intense band labeled ν_4 in Fig. 7a appears at 1400 cm^{-1} in both computational and experimental results, characterizing the asymmetrical stretching of the $-\text{N}=\text{N}-$ bond with contributions from the N (NH_2 moiety) to the Csp^2 atom of the azobenzene core vibrations. This fingerprint vibration was well predicted by the new ($n\text{NO}_2\pi^*\text{CT}$) transition belonging to the S_3 state introduced in the calculations of the Raman spectra. The vibrational wavenumber for ν_5 , described by the theoretical level (1334 cm^{-1}) including the $n\pi^*$ excitation (S_1 state), was consistent with the experimental measurement (1339 cm^{-1}). In the $1000\text{--}1200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ range, the presence of C–N and N–C vibration modes was observed. The symmetrical stretching of the C–N bond appears around 1187 cm^{-1} in the experimental Raman spectrum and computationally at 1212 cm^{-1} (see label ν_6 , Fig. 7a). On the other hand, ν_7 appears at 1135 cm^{-1} and reveals a C–N asymmetric mode. The vibration modes discussed above are depicted in Fig. 8, and the Huang-Rhys factor is shown in Fig. SI 38. In Fig. SI 38, the most intense Huang-Rhys factor appears at the frequency of 1400 cm^{-1} , where S is around 3.77, confirming a strong vibrational electronic coupling in the case of the $n\text{NO}_2 \rightarrow \pi^*\text{CT}$ transition ($S_0 \rightarrow S_3$ excitation), in spite of a small value of f . The theoretical details obtained with the CAM-B3LYP/cc-pVTZ level of theory depicted in Fig. 7b show an important contribution due to the fundamental state, which together with electronic excited state

coupling, allowance to the prediction of the final Raman spectra in agreement with laboratory determinations. The FCHT transition moment model was used for $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ in resonance, while the $S_0 \rightarrow S_3$ excitation in the pre-resonance, and the FC model for $S_0 \rightarrow S_2$ transitions on the resonance with incident frequency at 442 nm was applied to the **Azo-3** compound.

For the **Azo-19** derivative, the comparison between the experimental and theoretical Raman spectra was represented in the Fig. 9a. The Raman spectrum of compound **Azo-19**, was comparable with compound **Azo-3** with small differences, even if a different functional group in the para position of azobenzene core was attached. In particular, an intense peak appeared experimentally at 1590 , while from theoretical prediction around 1551 cm^{-1} , slightly underestimated, and represented the $-\text{N}=\text{N}-$ asymmetrical stretching vibration being stimulated by contribution of fundamental bands and $\pi\pi^*\text{CT}$ transition (Figs. 9a and 10). The ν_2 and ν_3 modes include a combination of different frequencies. The ν_2 mode in experimental spectrum was localized at 1515 cm^{-1} while from theoretical results at 1538 cm^{-1} . In the case of ν_3 label, experimentally was localized at 1448 cm^{-1} , and on the other hand, theoretically at 1446 cm^{-1} , being in a good agreement with experimental determinations. For both ν_2 and ν_3 vibration modes the contribution was given by fundamental state and less by S_1 ($n\pi^*$) excited state, (Fig. 9). The ν_3 mode has a higher intensity as compared to ν_2 , due to contribution of the S_1 vertical excitation state and here a symmetrical vibrational stretching of $-\text{N}=\text{N}-$ bond was observed. Like into the **Azo-3**, the ν_4 peak, represents an intense band, where the vibration mode is given by C-cp2-N(NO_2) asymmetric vibration coupled with asymmetric elongation of $-\text{N}=\text{N}-$ length, but with a slightly vibrational electronic coupling effect. This frequency was estimated in the same domain of frequency at 1400 cm^{-1} , by both computational and experimental determinations. The value for S ($S = 3.40$, Fig. SI 39) computed with CAM-B3LYP/cc-pVTZ method was also higher for this coupling electronic

Fig. 11. a) Comparison between experimental and theoretical Raman excitation profiles obtained from CAM-B3LYP/cc-pVTZ calculations for **Azo-44** compound; b) fundamental bands alongside the contributions from excited states and experimental measurements.

vibration. The ν_5 mode included specific aromatic vibration modes (no depicted here) and no observation was found for some units from the central C–N=N–C sequency of azobenzene core. The C–N vibration modes occur by asymmetrical stretching of ν_6 , and ν_7 (Fig. 10). The Huang Rhys factor depicted into Fig. SI 39 indicated the same trend, by higher value in the case of S_3 state like into **Azo-3** derivative. The FCHT transition moment model was employed for $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$, and FCHT, FC model for $S_0 \rightarrow S_2$ transitions on the resonance, and $S_0 \rightarrow S_3$ excitation in the pre-resonance with incident frequency at 442 nm was used to the

Azo-19 compound.

The **Azo 44** compound was added to the present study to confirm if the π - π -extended interplay of electron density can enhance the intensity of Raman spectra. The UV–Vis spectra (from Fig. SI 11) seem to be typically for pseudo-stilbene compounds. The experimental Raman profile depicted in Fig. 11 confirmed a strong band from experimental point of view in the region 1400–1800 cm^{-1} , in a similar way to **Azo-3** and **Azo-19** compounds, and the difference appears in the range of 1000–1200 cm^{-1} where the signal was smaller from experimental point of view for band intensity. The FCHT transition moment model was applied for $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$, and FCHT, FC model for $S_0 \rightarrow S_2$ transitions on the resonance, while the $S_0 \rightarrow S_3$ excitation in the pre-resonance with incident frequency at 442 nm of the **Azo-44** compound.

The vertical theoretical Raman spectra obtained by introduced the interplay of ground excited states from Fig. 11 reveal a good correlation with experiment if S_2 ($\pi\pi^*$ CT) state has been introduced in calculations. The most intense peak appeared experimentally at 1595 cm^{-1} and computational of 1566 cm^{-1} (see label ν_1). The enhanced intensity of the peak ν_1 can be due to the contribution of S_1 ($n\pi^*$). The intensity of band ν_2 was strongly overestimated by theoretical results using the CAM-B3LYP/cc-pVTZ method, but its position remains in the same range. The theoretical Raman spectra obtained introducing the interplay of ground excited states from Fig. 11 reveal a good correlation with experiment if S_2 ($\pi\pi^*$ CT) state has been taken in calculations. The most intense peak appeared experimentally at 1595 cm^{-1} and computational of 1566 cm^{-1} (see label ν_1). The enhanced intensity of the peak ν_1 can be due to the contribution of S_1 ($n\pi^*$). The intensity of band ν_2 was strongly overestimated by theoretical results using the CAM-B3LYP/cc-pVTZ method, but its position remains in the same wavenumber range. This strong enhanced peak obtained from theoretical point of view was assigned to contribution of S_3 state. Moreover, a very small contribution could be obtained from the S_2 state in the region of 1100–1500 cm^{-1} . However, an interference could appear between S_2 and S_3 states and therefore the last state can more enhanced. The combination mode between fundamental state with the electronic excited states could be observed from Fig. 11. In particular the ν_1 vibrational mode correspond for an –N=N– asymmetrical stretching mode, while ν_2 is due to the asymmetric vibration between NO_2 moiety with vicinal ring (Fig. 12). The Huang Rhys factor showed same trends like into compound **Azo-3** and **Azo-19**, but the value of S term was around $S = 1.87$ (Fig. SI 40). In these conditions, the Raman spectra of the **Azo-44** was computed with VGF (Vertical Gradient and Frequencies) method in comparison with the rest of calculations where the VG level was applied. This method was selected because allow changes of the normal frequencies with relating to the electronic state [58].

Unless specified the theoretical Raman spectra obtained with CAM-B3LYP level were scaled with 0.9870 factor according to data from Table 1. Theoretical results indicated in the Raman spectra of the azobenzene derivatives under study an $|0\rangle \rightarrow |1\rangle$ electronic–vibrational coupling appear, confirming a combination mode between the fundamental state and electronic excitations.

Fig. 12. Representation of the vibrational modes of **Azo-44** compound computed with the CAM-B3LYP/cc-pVTZ method.

4. Conclusion

The Raman spectra of some azobenzene derivatives were considered for theoretical and experimental investigation. Experimental Raman measurements showed an enhancement of intensity when the incident light at 442 nm was in resonance with an electronic transition, and theoretical calculations exhibited a similar trend. To mimic the experimental conditions, a systematic study was conducted using multiple levels of theory employing quantum mechanics DFT approaches.

A detailed examination of vertical transitions highlighted the significant roles of the excitation process of azobenzene derivatives. Theoretical findings confirmed the presence of $n\pi^*$, $\pi\pi^*$ for **Azo**, $\pi\pi^*$ CT, $n\pi^*$ CT, $n\pi^*$ for **Azo-4**, and $\pi\pi^*$ CT, $n\pi^*$ CT, $\pi\pi^*$ for **Azo-3**, **Azo-19**, and **Azo-44** derivatives. In particular, in the case of the azobenzene derivatives **Azo-3**, **Azo-19** and **Azo-44**, in addition to the presence of the charge transfer states, new states were also identified that lead to the effect of quenching of CT effect. These states have been confirmed for the first time in these compounds, and can give significant contributions in the Raman spectra. Based on vertical transition results, theoretical Raman spectra were computed by combining vibrational modes from the ground and first excited states ($S_0 \rightarrow S_n$), thereby demonstrating the signature of the contribution of the excited states contributing to vibrational resonance Raman spectral fingerprints on resonance and pre-resonance interplay. The HT transition moment model was applied to obtain theoretical Raman spectra, including contributions from dark transitions, aligning well with experimental measurements in the 1400–1800 cm^{-1} wavenumber range within fingerprint region. However, this model introduced additional peaks in the 800–1000 cm^{-1} Raman spectra. The FC level was selected for calculating theoretical Raman spectra, introducing the contributions from bright transitions, yielding results correlated with experimental data in the 1000–1400 cm^{-1} domain within the 800–1800 cm^{-1} fingerprint range. Qualitative overlap between theoretical results and experimental data confirms the presence of combination modes involving transitions between fundamental and electronically excited states. These interactions occur when the excited energy of a molecule is distributed among several vibrational modes, as demonstrated in this study. Furthermore, it was demonstrated that transitions with forbidden character, despite very small oscillator strength value, can be evinced using Raman spectroscopy, providing unique signatures in the spectrum. It is recommended that such transitions are tuned to be in resonance with the laser frequency used in vibrational scattering determinations. The methodology described in this article proves useful for interpreting experimental Raman spectra, particularly for azobenzene derivatives.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Dragos Lucian Isac: Writing – original draft, Investigation, Validation, Formal analysis. **Emilian Rosca:** Software, Formal analysis. **Anton Airinei:** Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **Elena Laura Ursu:** Validation. **Razvan Puf:** Methodology, Investigation. **Isabela Costinela Man:** Methodology. **Andrei Neamtu:** Formal analysis. **Aatto Laaksonen:** Validation, Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by a grant of the Romanian Ministry of Research, Innovation and Digitization, CNCS/CCCDI-UEFISCDI: Project number PN-III-P1-1.1-PD2021-0060 within PNCDDI III (FingerprintAZO) and by European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation

programme under grant agreement No 101086667, project Bio-Mat4CAST. AL acknowledges Swedish Research Council (2019-03865). DLI acknowledges technical support provided by FreeYa Mind Campus, and technical support provided by Swedish National Infrastructure for Computing (SNIC) at PDC.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.saa.2025.125828>.

Data availability

All data in this paper are provided in the attached file ([Supporting information](#)). The theoretical, experimental data and SpectraCorrM code are shared with the community at <https://github.com/dragos-isac/FingerprintAZO.git>.

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